

Removal of Ni(II) Ion from Aqueous Solution using Chitosan Nanoparticles derived from Blue Crab (*Callinectes sapidus*) Shells

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ABSTRACT

Pulverised shells of blue crabs (*Callinectes sapidus*) were demineralized using 0.7 M HCl, and the protein content was removed by treating with 1.2 M NaOH to obtain chitin. The obtained chitin was de-acetylated to chitosan using 50% NaOH at 100°C for 3 h. The synthesised chitosan was converted to nanoparticles by tripolyphosphate (TPP). The chitosan nanoparticles were characterised using Fourier Transform Infra-Red (FTIR), Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), and X-Ray Diffraction (XRD). The point of zero charge (pzc) was at pH 6.3. Batch adsorption was carried out on Ni(II) aqueous solution using chitosan nanoparticles as adsorbent. The data obtained were subjected to kinetic, isotherm and thermodynamic studies. The results fitted well into pseudo-second order model and Freundlich isotherm, having high correlation coefficient (R²) values. The thermodynamics of the system showed that ΔH , ΔS and ΔG were negative: implying exothermic process; low degree of randomness; and spontaneity of the adsorption process.

Keywords: *Thermodynamics, chitosan nanoparticles, isotherms, crab shells, wastewater, adsorption,*

INTRODUCTION

Recycling of wastewater has been considered possible as a result of advancement in science and technology [1]. The development has in good measure improved the quantity of water available for domestic, industrial, and agricultural purposes. Increased population, uncontrolled migration, industrial revolution, refuse and sewage discharge from homes and factories have played a major role in making water bodies unwholesome for use. Contamination of water by heavy metals is a global issue which poses health risk since the elements are not biodegradable [2].

Electroplating industries, ceramic industries, and other chemical industries discharge large volume of wastewater polluted with heavy metals (e.g. Pb, Zn, Cu, Ni, Cr, and Cd) into the environment [3, 4, 5, 6]. Heavy metals may bio-accumulate in living organisms through constant ingestion. Lead (Pb), when present in human body, even at low concentration damages vital organs. Body immune systems are also targeted by the toxic lead. Lead in high concentration in the body causes insomnia, persistent headache, body irritation, convulsions and seizures [7, 8]. Copper on the hand in high concentration causes anaemia. It damages various organs such as liver and kidney in human body. Over-exposure to copper causes Wilson's disease in human. The presence of copper in aquatic habitats is poisonous to aquatic organisms living in them [9, 10].

Various processes such as coagulation-flocculation [11, 12], membrane-filtration [13], and oxidation [14, 15] have been employed to remove organic pollutants from wastewaters. However, Ion exchange, electro-coagulation, and electrolytic reduction processes have been employed for the removal of heavy metals in wastewater. Adsorption process is now popular as an effective method of removing heavy metals [16, 17, 18].

Chitosan due to its exceptional chelating ability appears to be a potent adsorbent [19]. It is a copolymer of glucosamine and N-acetyl glucosamine units [20] which can be obtained by de-acetylating chitin. Chitosan structure closely resembles the structure of cellulose, except that the hydroxyl group at C₂ position in cellulose is replaced by amino group. Chitosan exhibits

antibacterial, antifungal, and antiviral properties. It can be made into film, fibre, and hydrogel [21, 22]. Chitosan finds applications in medical field, it has been extensively used in cosmetic, food, pulp and paper, and textile industries [23, 24]. Chitosan is good for producing metal complexes as effective protein coagulants [25]. Chitosan nanoparticle was chosen for this research work because of the large surface area to volume ratio inherent from the reduction of particle size. The reduction in the particle size would expose several active sites on the adsorbent surface, which will invariably improve the efficiency of the adsorbent to remove Ni(II) ion from aqueous solution.

METHODOLOGY

Materials

Sodium tripolyphosphate (TPP), hydrochloric acid (HCl), sodium hydroxide (NaOH) pellets, acetic acid, and hydrated NiSO₄·6H₂O used in this research were of analytical grade, purchased from Sigma Aldrich Chemical Company. Blue crab shells were collected from a local market in Lagos, Nigeria.

Adsorbent preparation

Blue crab shells were dried and ground into powder. The powder was demineralised using 0.7 M HCl (at 65°C for 3 h) and washed severally with distilled water. The protein content of the sample was removed using 1.2 M NaOH (at 65°C for 30 min). The resulting sample was washed to neutrality using distilled water to obtain chitin. Chitosan was obtained by de-acetylating chitin with 50% NaOH (at 100°C for 3 h), washed and dried at 65°C. The resulting product was converted to chitosan nanoparticles by dissolving in 1 M acetic acid. The mixture was filtered and the nanomaterial was precipitated by the addition of sodium tripolyphosphate (TPP) in a drop-wise manner. The chitosan nanoparticles were washed with distilled water and filtered using sinter glass (size G-3). The final product was characterised using Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) and Fourier Transform Infra-Red (FTIR).

Batch adsorption process

Adsorption process was carried out using chitosan nanoparticles as adsorbent for the removal of Ni(II) ion from aqueous solution. 50 mg/L of metal solution was prepared from the stock solution (1000 mg/L), 50 mL was measured into conical flasks and the pH was adjusted appropriately. 0.5 g of the adsorbent was added to each beaker, the mixture was agitated at regular interval for 6 h, filtered and analysed using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS Buck Scientific 210). Point of zero charge was investigated by dissolving 0.1 g of the adsorbent in 50 mL 0.1 M KNO₃ as variation in pH was recorded after 24 h. Contact time and concentration studies were carried out simultaneously using the optimum pH. Effect of temperature variation (room temp, 35, 45, 55, and 65 °C) was investigated using the optimal pH and time. The amount of uptake by metal ion was calculated using equation 1.

$$q_e = \frac{(C_0 - C_e)V}{m} \quad (1)$$

Where q_e (mg/g) is the quantity of metal ion uptake, C_0 (mg/L) is the initial metal ion concentration, C_e (mg/L) is the non-adsorbed molecules left in the adsorbate, V (mL) is the volume of metal ion solution, and m (g) is the mass of the adsorbent.

Percentage uptake was calculated using equation 2.

$$\text{Metal removal (\%)} = \frac{(C_0 - C_e)}{C_0} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

FTIR, XRD and SEM analyses of chitosan nanoparticles

The chitosan nanoparticles were characterised using Fourier Transform Infra-red, Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), and X-Ray Diffraction as presented in Fig. 1, 2 and 3, respectively. The following peaks were observed from the FTIR spectrum: 3447.87 cm⁻¹, representing O-H stretch of alcoholic and phenolic groups; 2931.90 cm⁻¹, denoting C-H stretch, 1643.41, 1435.09 and 873.78 cm⁻¹, representing N-H bend, C-C stretch (in ring) and N-H wag of primary and secondary amines respectively; and 1050.28 cm⁻¹, denoting C-O stretch of alcohols. The scanning electron micrograph of chitosan nanoparticles is presented in Fig. 2. The image shows the nature of the surface of the adsorbent, the particles appear distinct and form a cluster of many fine particles. The scale of the micrograph was 20 μm. Fig. 3 shows the XRD image of chitosan nanoparticles. The two major peaks of chitosan often appear at 2θ = 10° and 20°. However, the peak at 2θ = 10° shifted forward to 13° while the peak at 2θ = 20° did not shift. The shifting in the angle could be due to the fact that the chitosan in its pure form has been chemically modified using TPP to give

chitosan nanoparticles.

Figure 1: FTIR spectrum of chitosan nanoparticles

The chemical conversion caused other conspicuous peaks to show on the XRD image (Fig. 3). The particle size of the chitosan nanoparticles was 9.94 nm.

Figure 2: SEM image of chitosan nanoparticles

Figure 3: X-Ray Diffractogram chitosan nanoparticles

pH studies and point of zero charge (pzc)

Effect of pH on the removal process of Ni(II) ions was presented in Fig. 4. It was observed that there was a slow removal of metal ion at low pH which later progressed considerably as the pH increased. The low removal of metal ions at low pH could be as a result of an increased competition between the species in the adsorbate and protons. Zamil *et al.* [26] reported that increase in pH leads to increase in total number of negative groups available for the binding of metal ions which invariably leads to reduced competition between proton and metal ions. From the results, it was observed that Ni(II) ion removal peaked at pH 6. Godea *et al.* [27] reported that Ni(II) ion forms a precipitate at pH greater than 8; and Kurniawan *et al.* [28] reported that precipitate of Cu(OH)₂ tends to be formed at pH > 6.

Figure 4: Effects of pH on Ni(II) ion removal

The point of zero charge of any adsorbent is the pH in which the net charge at the surface of the adsorbent is zero [29]. Fig. 5 shows that the point of zero charge of chitosan nanoparticles occurred at pH 6.3. At this point, the magnitude of the positive charge at the surface were at equilibrium with the negative charge at the surface of the

adsorbent.

Figure 5: The point of zero charge of chitosan nanoparticles
 Fiol and Villaescusa [29] reported that if the pH of the solution is higher than the point of zero charge, then the surface charge of the solid adsorbent will be negative which can then attract metal ions (cations). Also, if the pH of point of zero charge is higher than the pH of the solution, the adsorbent surface charge therefore becomes positive, and this will thereby draw negative ions onto the surface. Adsorptive system is therefore a competitive process between hydrogen/hydroxyl ions and the adsorbate species, in which negatively charged species are better adsorbed at lower pH and positively charged species are better adsorbed at higher pH.

Contact time and kinetic studies at different concentration

Effects of time variation on the removal of Ni(II) ion from aqueous solution were studied alongside concentration as presented in Fig. 6. It was observed that increase in time favoured the uptake of nickel ion, this was as a result of many active sites that were readily available for metal binding. The number of active sites is most likely to reduce as the metal ions continue to adhere to the adsorbent pores. In Fig. 6, there was a rapid uptake of metal ion at the initial stage which increased considerably and peaked at 120 min for the different concentrations under study. A slight decrease occurred after optimum time (120 min), this could

be as a result of further agitation which could render some of the adsorbed species mobile, and thus return into the solution.

Figure 6: Contact time studies for the uptake of Ni(II) ion at different concentrations

The data obtained from the contact time studies with varied concentrations were evaluated using kinetic models (pseudo-first order and pseudo-second order).

Lagergren [30] expressed pseudo-first order kinetic model as;

$$\frac{dq}{dt} = k_{ad}(q_e - qt) \quad (3)$$

Where q_e (mg/g) is the metal ion uptake at equilibrium, q_t (mg/g) is the metal ion uptake at time t , and k_{ad} (L/min) represents first order rate constant. Equation 3 was integrated (using boundary conditions: $t = 0$ to t and $q = 0$ to q_e) to give a linear expression (equation 4).

$$\text{Log}(q_e - q_t) = \text{log}q_e - \frac{k_{ad}}{2.303}t \quad (4)$$

Log ($q_e - q_t$) was plotted against t (min) for the removal process of Ni(II) ion as presented in Fig. 7. The values of q_e and k_{ad} were extrapolated from the intercept and the slope of the plot respectively, and the results are presented in Table 1.

Pseudo-second order kinetic model is expressed in equation 5;

$$\frac{t}{q} = \frac{1}{k_2 q_e^2} + \frac{1}{q_e}t \quad (5)$$

Where q_e (mg/g) and k_2 ($\text{g mg}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$) are the metal ion uptake at equilibrium and pseudo-second order rate constant. t/q (min/mg) was plotted against t (min) as presented in Fig. 8, the values of q_e and k_2 were estimated from the slope and the intercept, respectively. Table 1 shows the parameters of pseudo-first order and pseudo-second order kinetic models. It was observed that the correlation coefficient R^2 for pseudo-second order model approached unity unlike R^2 of pseudo-first order that was not tending to one. Comparing the experimental $q_{e \text{ Exp}}$ (mg/g) and the estimated $q_{e \text{ Est}}$ (mg/g) of pseudo-first order and pseudo-second order kinetic models, it was observed that $q_{e \text{ exp}}$ and $q_{e \text{ Est}}$ values for pseudo-second order were close to each other, whereas, there was a wide margin between values of $q_{e \text{ exp}}$ and $q_{e \text{ Est}}$ for pseudo-first order kinetic model, the implication is that, pseudo-second order kinetic model was more suited than pseudo-second order kinetic model. Reports have suggested that most adsorption processes are always in consonance with pseudo-second order kinetic model [31, 32].

Figure 7: Pseudo-first order kinetic plot for Ni(II) ion removal

Figure 8: Pseudo-second order kinetic plot for Ni(II) ion removal

Table 1: Kinetic parameters for the removal of Ni(II) ion

Pseudo-first order					Pseud-second order		
C_o (mg/L)	Q_e Exp. (mg/g)	Q_e Est. (mg/g)	K_1 (min^{-1})	R^2	Q_e Est. (mg/g)	K_2 (gmg^{-1})	R^2
25	2.114	0.443	0.009	0.431	2.114	0.097	0.999
50	4.194	1.027	0.005	0.404	3.896	0.109	0.995
75	5.343	0.761	0.006	0.306	5.277	0.052	0.999
100	6.882	0.561	-0.002	0.003	5.893	-0.031	0.993
200	12.893	1.338	0.002	0.055	11.728	-0.039	0.995

Initial metal ion concentration and isotherm studies

Initial metal ion concentrations were varied with time for the removal process of Ni(II) ion. It was observed that increase in the

initial metal ion concentration did not favour metal removal as there was a decrease in the uptake, this could be due to an increase in adsorbate concentration without corresponding increase in the adsorbent dosage. Futralan *et al.* [33] and Kamari and Ngah [34] reported that, a number of adsorption active sites were readily available at the start, as a result of this, metal ion uptake would be rapid, before slowly attaining an equilibrium. Cybelle *et al.* [35] reported that when adsorption process approaches equilibrium, active sites on the surface are almost filled up with metal ions. The unfilled sites on the surface will not be readily available anymore, and become more difficult for metal ions to adhere onto the sites because of repulsion forces at the interface.

The generated data from concentration studies were subjected to Langmuir, Freundlich, Temkin and Dubinin-Radushkevich models. Langmuir isotherm is a widely used expression for metal ion uptake in adsorption process as it assumes that a particular adsorbent has a definite amount of active sites with the same energy level for monolayer coverage [36].

Langmuir model is given in equation 6;

$$\frac{C_e}{q_e} = \frac{1}{bq_m} + \frac{C_e}{q_m} \quad (6)$$

Where q_m (mgg^{-1}) and b (mLmg^{-1}) are the maximum adsorption capacity for monolayer coverage and Langmuir constant for the association of adsorbate species onto the active sites [37]. Fig. 9 shows the Langmuir plots for Ni(II) ion removal. The values of q_m and b (Table 2) were extrapolated from the intercepts and the slopes, respectively. Correlation coefficient R^2 did not tend to one which implies that Langmuir model was not in totality obeyed. Another important parameter that dictates the favourability of Langmuir isotherm model is R_L (equation 7), a separation factor which can be deduced from Langmuir expression;

$$R_L = \frac{1}{1 + bC_o} \quad (7)$$

Where b and C_o represent constant of Langmuir adsorption

equilibrium (mL/mg) and initial metal ion concentration (mg/L). When $R_L = 0$, it is an irreversible process; favourable when $0 < R_L < 1$; unfavourable when $R_L > 1$; and linear when $R_L = 1$. In Table 2, the values of R_L at different time interval were less than 1 but greater than 0 which implied favourable adsorption process in the removal of the metal ions.

Freundlich model (equation 8) is based on the assumption of reversible adsorption of heterogeneous systems [34].

$$\log q_e = \log K_F + \frac{1}{n_F} \log C_e \quad (8)$$

Where k_F (mgg^{-1}) is the Freundlich adsorption capacity; and $1/n_F$ represents Freundlich heterogeneity factor also denoted as b_F . The parameter, b_F describes the intensity of adsorption on the heterogeneity of the surface. The solid phase becomes more heterogeneous when b_F tends to zero [39]. Fig. 10 shows the Freundlich plot of Ni(II) ion removal process. Freundlich constants; k_F and b_F were estimated from the intercept and slope, respectively, and the values are presented in Table 2. Correlation coefficient (R^2) for the removal of Ni(II) ion tended to one, suggesting that the data fitted well into Freundlich model which implies heterogeneous system. The heterogeneity of the system is established when the value of $1/n_F$ falls between zero and one, suggesting a strong bond between metal ion and adsorbent [40].

Figure 9: Langmuir plots of Ni(II) ion removal at different time interval

Figure 10: Freundlich plots of Ni(II) ion removal at different time interval

Temkin [41] gave a linear expression for the energy involved in adsorption process due to the relationship among the interacting

entities. Temkin model points to the evenly distribution of the energies available for binding in all the active sites. Temkin model (equation 9) is often applied in its linear form [42] (Temkin and Phoyez, 1940).

$$q_e = B \ln A + B \ln C_e \quad (9)$$

$$B = \frac{RT}{b} \quad (10)$$

Where A (L/g) is Temkin isotherm constant, b (J/mol) is a constant related to heat energy available in sorption, R is gas

Table 2: Isotherm parameters for the removal of Ni(II) ion

Time (min)	Langmuir parameters					Freundlich parameters			Temkin parameters		
	Q _{max} (mg/g)	b	R _L	K _L (dm ³ /g)	R ²	K _F (dm ³ /g)	1/n _F or b _F	R ²	A	B	R ²
5	21.277	0.008	0.712	0.172	0.767	0.351	0.715	0.990	0.146	7.432	0.871
15	24.096	0.007	0.730	0.179	0.747	0.341	0.740	0.993	0.144	7.952	0.869
30	20.325	0.010	0.652	0.217	0.906	0.419	0.707	0.999	0.167	7.816	0.909
60	21.186	0.010	0.658	0.219	0.900	0.417	0.714	0.999	0.167	7.988	0.906
90	26.110	0.011	0.643	0.291	0.740	0.599	0.595	0.980	0.201	9.205	0.871
120	17.762	0.027	0.424	0.484	0.832	1.069	0.561	0.960	0.395	7.495	0.868
180	18.762	0.025	0.448	0.462	0.826	0.987	0.585	0.976	0.360	7.821	0.868
240	17.036	0.024	0.455	0.408	0.726	0.994	0.551	0.946	0.362	7.103	0.811
300	15.060	0.026	0.436	0.390	0.779	0.980	0.532	0.960	0.362	6.536	0.836
360	15.267	0.024	0.456	0.367	0.794	0.934	0.537	0.970	0.344	6.504	0.840

Figure 11: Temkin plots of Ni(II) ion removal at different time interval

Dubinin–Radushkevich (D-R) isotherm as described by Horsfall *et al.* [43] is expressed in equation 11, its linearized form is presented in equation 12:

$$q_e = q_D \exp(-B_D [RT \ln(1 + \frac{1}{C_{eq}})]^2) \quad (11)$$

$$\ln q_e = \ln q_D - 2B_D RT \ln(1 + \frac{1}{C_e}) \quad (12)$$

Where B_D and q_D are the sorption free energy per mole of the adsorbate and the constant of Dubinin-Radushkevich isotherm for the surface of the adsorbent, respectively. R is gas constant (8.314 Jmol⁻¹K⁻¹) and T is temperature in Kelvin. Correlation coefficient (R²) for Ni(II) ion removal was 0.8447 indicating some level of conformity to D-R model. The value of sorption free energy (B_D) was 6 × 10⁻⁷ J²mol⁻¹, while the Value of q_D was 2.431 mg/g which denoted good adsorption capacity. Igwe and Abia [44] reported that the higher the value of q_D, the higher the adsorption capacity within the system.

The energy, E involved in the removal process is expressed in equation (13).

$$E = \frac{1}{(2B_D)^2} \quad (13)$$

The energy (E) often times predicts the type of adsorption process. In this study, the value of E was 0.9130 kJ/mol which was well below 8 kJmol⁻¹, implying physical adsorption.

Thermodynamic studies

constant (8.314 J/molK), and T (K) is the absolute temperature. The quantity of uptake, q_e (mg/g) was plotted against lnC_e and the results are presented in Fig. 11. The R² values at different time interval showed some levels of conformity to Temkin model as presented in Table 2.

Thermodynamic parameters for the removal process of Ni(II) ion were estimated using vant' Hoff expression (equation 14).

$$\ln K_d = \frac{\Delta S}{R} - \frac{\Delta H}{RT} \quad (14)$$

ΔH and ΔS are the enthalpy and entropy changes, respectively. The parameters were calculated from the slope and the intercept of lnK_d plotted against 1/T. R is gas constant (8.314 kJ/molK), T is temperature in Kelvin, and K_d is the thermodynamic constant.

Gibb's free energy is expressed in equation 15;

$$\Delta G = -RT \ln K_d \quad (15)$$

Where ΔG is the change in Gibb's free energy of sorption process, R is gas constant (8.314 kJ/molK), T is temperature in Kelvin, and K_d is the thermodynamic constant of equilibrium.

The thermodynamic studies showed that ΔS was negative (-122.590 Jmol⁻¹K⁻¹) which implied association between the adsorbate and the adsorbent, the negative value also offered minimum restriction for the adherence of the adsorbate onto the adsorbent active sites. ΔH value was negative (-40.5291 kJmol⁻¹) which indicated exothermic reaction. The values of ΔG at 301, 308, 318, 328 and 338 K were negative; having -4.1680, -2.8544, -3.4950, -2.1828, and -2.2492 kJmol⁻¹K⁻¹, respectively. This implied that the adsorption process was feasible and spontaneous.

CONCLUSION

Crabs shells are underutilised materials which often times constitute nuisance to the environment when disposed indiscriminately. Although the shells are waste materials from crabs, but they can still be harnessed to produce chitosan (a natural polymer), which could be very useful for wastewater treatment. The efficacy of chitosan nanoparticles to remove heavy metals from aqueous solution has been investigated in this research. The kinetics of the process showed that the data fitted well into pseudo-second order kinetic model, while the isotherm studies showed that the data generated fitted well into Freundlich isotherm. The thermodynamic studies revealed that exothermic energy was involved, while negative ΔG meant that the process was feasible and spontaneous.

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